

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

№4 (2)

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

2026
APREL

Milliy nashrlar

OAK: <https://oak.uz/pages/4802>

05.00.00 - Texnika fanlari

08.00.00 - Iqtisodiyot fanlar

Google Scholar

OPEN ACCESS

ULRICHSWEB™
GLOBAL SERIALS DIRECTORY

Academic Resource Index
ResearchBib

ISSN INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CYBERLENINKA

OpenAIRE

ROAD

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

BASE

Crossref

НАУЧНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ
БИБЛИОТЕКА
LIBRARY.RU

ISSN: 3060-463X

РЭУ.РФ
РОССИЙСКИЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Elektron nashr, 2026-yil, aprel.

Bosh muharrir:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, DSc, professor

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Shakarov Zafar G'afarovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, PhD, dotsent

Tahrir hay'ati:

Abduraxmanov Kalendar Xodjayevich, O'z FA akademigi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Mahammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor,

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

Jo'raeva Malohat Muhammadovna, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor.

Yusupov Maxamadamin Abduxamidovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor

Kalonova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent

Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanzakovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor.

Karimova Nilufar Sadirdin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Norboyev Odil Abrayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanzakovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Karimova Nilufar Sadirdin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Pardaev Umidjon Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc)

muhandislik & iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.08.06 – "G'ildirakli va gusenisali mashinalar va ularni ishlatish" (texnika fanlari)
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

1. Toshkent shahridagi G.V.Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
2. Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
3. Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
4. Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
5. Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
6. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
7. Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

BYUDJET SUBYEKTLARI ISHTIROKINI QISQARTIRISH ASOSIDA KREDIT RISKINI BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	16
PhD. Mahmudov Rahimjon Hamid o'g'li	
MINTAQA IQTISODIYOTI TARMOQLARINI KLASTERLASHTIRISH SALOHIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING EMPIRIK MODEL: STATISTIK VA EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL.....	25
Ollokulova Feruza Mansurovna, Abdurahmonov Abdulaziz Maxmudovich	
XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARDA PUL OQIMLARI AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY MEXANIZMLARI.....	30
Atamurodov Saidmurad Yaxyoyevich, Sindarova Aziza Musurmon qizi	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISHNI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	42
Xasanov Sardor Xazratkulovich	
IQTISODIY O'SISH SIFATI VA UNI KO'RSATKICHLARINING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI.....	50
Axmedov Xasanjon Muxamadovich	
IQTISODIY O'SISH SIFATI VA UNI KO'RSATKICHLARINING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI.....	55
Axmedov Xasanjon Muxamadovich	
ENERGIYA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING KORXONALAR RENTABELLIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	60
Hayitov Jamshid Xolboyevich	
KREDITLASH MEXANIZMINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNING TARIXIY RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI.....	65
Ortiqov Husan Usmonaliyevich	
DAVLAT SEKTORIDA ICHKI AUDIT FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	70
Xamidova Zarifa Urol qizi	
ISTE'MOL NARXLARI INDEKSINI MODELLASHTIRISH VA PROGNOZLASHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	74
Ismailova Shaxnoza Uktamovna	
XIZMATLAR SEKTORI RIVOJLANISHINING KAMBAG'ALLIKKA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASI VA KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMI.....	77
Dawletmuratov Adilbay Mirzaboyevich	
BIZNES JARAYONLARINI MONITORING QILISH TIZIMINING HOZIRGI HOLATI TAHLILI.....	84
Dadajonova Madina Ravshan qizi	
ISTE'MOL NARXLARI INDEKSINI MODELLASHTIRISH VA PROGNOZLASHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	89
Ismailova Shaxnoza Uktamovna	
MINTAQA IQTISODIYOTI TARMOQLARINI KLASTERLASHTIRISH SALOHIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING EMPIRIK MODEL: STATISTIK VA EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL.....	94
Ollokulova Feruza Mansurovna, Abdurahmonov Abdulaziz	
ENERGIYA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING KORXONALAR RENTABELLIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	100
Hayitov Jamshid Xolboyevich	
IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF BANKS' GREEN FINANCING IN UZBEKISTAN AND KAZAKHSTAN.....	105
Maxmudov Rahimjon	
MAHALLIY BUDJETLAR MUSTAQILLIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA YANADA OSHIRISH.....	109
Abduraxmonova Gulmira	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA MOLIVAVIY HISOBOTLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH: MUAMMOLAR VA YECHIMLAR.....	114
Teshabayev Dilmurod Boxodir o'g'li	

FARG 'ONA VILOYATINING INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHI.....	120
Tuychieva Odina Nabiyevena	
INDICATORS OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE "GREEN" ECONOMY.....	131
Mirzaev Kulmamat Djanzakovich	
KREDITLASH MEXANIZMINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNING TARIXIY RIVOJLANISH BOSQICH LARI.....	140
Ortiqov Husan Usmonaliyevich	
KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNING XALQARO TAJRIBASI VA UNING QIYOSIY TAHLILI.....	144
Shakirova Gulbaxor Sharipdjanovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISHNI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	149
Xasanov Sardor Xazratkulovich	
IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNING INSTITUSIONAL ASOSLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING XORIJ DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	156
Odinayev Ravzatullo Asatulloevich	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINING MOLIVAVIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	161
Karimov Alibek Valievich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA FRANCHAYZING TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA PLATFORMA MODELLARI VA ULARNING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	167
Xodjaye Anvar Rasulovich, Nasimov Dilshodbek Hotam o'g'li	
"O'ZBEKISTON GTL" MAHSULOTLARINING FIZIK-KIMYOVIY XOSSALARI VA ULARNI KOMPOUDIRLASH ASOSIDA EKOLOGIK TOZA YOQILG'ILAR OLIISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	173
Ro'ziyev Aliakbar, Hayitov Ruslan, Mavlonov Shohrux	
HUDUDIY MEHNAT BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA AVTOSERVIS KORXONALARINING ROLI.....	179
Marqayev Xurshid Aliqulovich	
ASOSIY VOSITALAR AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	183
Zaripova Sayohat Zafarovna	
XIZMATLAR SOHASINI BOSHQARISHDAGI MUAMMOLAR VA YECHIMLAR: AGROTURIZM VA RAQAMLI XIZMATLAR ASOSIDA TAHLIL (ANDIJON VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	188
Oktamjonova Gulira'no Ikromjon qizi	
BUXORO VILOYATI UY XO'JALIKLARI HAYOT SIFATI VA IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY AHVOLI: SO'ROVNOMA NATIJALARI TAHLILI.....	192
Nizomov Asliddin, Musulmonova Shahlo, Izzatullayeva Ma'mura	
DIRECTIONS FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES..	199
Mirzaev Kulmamat Djanzakovich	
QORA METALLURGIYA SANOATI VA ULARNING ISHLATILISHI.....	203
Sarimsakov Alisher Ubaydullaevich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA AHOLI BANDLIGINING IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI.....	209
Yusupov Farhod Adamboyevich	
TASVIRLARDAN YO'L BELGILARINI TANIB OLIISH ALGORITMLARI VA DASTURIY VOSITASINI ISHLAB CHIQISH.....	214
Toyirov Akbar Xasanovich, Yuldoshov Abdurahmon Baxtiyorovich	
OLIIY TA'LIMNI MOLIVALASHTIRISHNING ILG'OR XORIJIY TAJRIBASI: SINGAPUR MISOLIDA.....	218
Kurbanov Baxodir Negmatullayevich	

MA'LUMOTLARGA ASOSLANGAN TURIZM BOSHQARUVI: O'ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONLARI.....	222
Ashurova Shaxnoza Almasovna	
DAVLAT XARIDLARI BO'YICHA BYUDJET MABLAG'LARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI ICHKI AUDITNING ANALITIK KO'RSATKICHLARI ASOSIDA BAHOLASH.....	226
Meliboyev Askar Eshmuratovich	
ГЛИНИСТЫЕ СЛАНЦЫ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОГО И ЮЖНОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА КАК СЫРЬЕВАЯ СМЕСЬ ДЛЯ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА ПОРТЛАНДЦЕМЕНТА.....	231
Карабаев А.М., Абдуллаева Д.Ф., Абдуллаев У.Х. Андакулова Н.Н.	
ЦИФРОВАЯ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ СИСТЕМЫ МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА КАЧЕСТВА НА ПРОМЫШЛЕННОМ ПРЕДПРИЯТИИ.....	237
Садиков Жaxonгир Носирджанович, Даулетмуратова Дилбар Калмуқанмед кизи	
РАЗРАБОТКА МЕХАТРОННОГО МОДУЛЯ ДЛЯ ВЫРАВНИВАНИЯ ПОВЕРХНОСТИ МЕТАЛЛА ПОСЛЕ ЗАЛИВКИ.....	243
Мирджуроев Сарвар Алишер угли	
MAHALLIY BUDJET DAROMADLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNING TA'SIRI ..	246
Isoqov Zafarjon Zokirjonovich	
AGROKLASTERLAR SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING EKONOMETRIK MODELLARI	250
O'rinboev Ulug'bek Otabekovich	
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПОРИСТОЙ СТРУКТУРЫ И ВЛАГОПОГЛОЩАЮЩИХ СВОЙСТВ КОМПОЗИТНОГО ВЯЖУЩЕГО	259
Тургунбаев Уринбек, Шарипова Дилафруз, Худойбердиев Жамшид	
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ НАПРЯЖЕННО-ДЕФОРМИРОВАННОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ЯЧЕЙКИ СВЕТОПРОЗРАЧНОГО ОГРАЖДЕНИЯ ПРИ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИИ ЛОКАЛЬНОЙ СЕЙСМИЧЕСКОЙ НАГРУЗКИ.....	265
Давронов Олимбек, Туляганов Азиз	
PAHTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARNING EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	271
Mamasoliyev G'ayratbek Maxamadyusupovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING TURIZMDA MOHIYATI VA AHAMIYATI.....	276
Abdullayeva Zulfiya Izzatovna	
MINTAQAVIY SANOAT KORXONALARINING BIZNES JARAYONLARINI TAHLIL QILISH VA BAHOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI (BPM, LEAN VA SIX SIGMA YONDASHUVLARI MISOLIDA) ..	279
Azimova Maxfuza Rashidovna	
QURILISH SANOATI KORXONALARINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI VA ULARNI EKOLOGIK BOSHQARISH TAMOIYILLARI	284
Xolov Xamza Tojiddinovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA AHOLINI QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI BILAN TA'MINLASHNING IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH: EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL VA PROGNOZLASH	292
Matjonov Bekjon Ravshonbekovich, Ibragimova Nodira Kadamovna	
A THEORETICAL MODEL LINKING GENDER EQUALITY AND MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY.....	297
Ochilova Intizor Sadikovna	
QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR PORTFELIDAN KUTILAYOTGAN DAROMADGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLARNI EKONOMETRIK MODEL ORQALI BAHOLASH.....	303
Sindarov Fazliddin Kaxramonovich	
MAMLAKAT KIMYO SANOATIDAGI KORXONALAR FAOLIYATIDA RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH JARAYONI VA ULARNING TAHLILI.....	312
Odilova Malika Abdushukur qizi	

RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI ISHLAB CHIQRISH SANOATIGA JORIY ETISH	317
Abdivoyitova Sarvinoz Abduxayit qizi, Maxmudov Abrorxon Axmadxonovich	
NODAVLAT OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA BOSHQARUV HISOB TIZIMINI TASHKIL ETISHNING NAZARIY VA AMALIY JIHATLARI	321
Xojiboyev Muxiddin Shodimuxamedovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING INVESTITSION FAOLIGINI OSHIRISHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI TAHLILI.....	326
Dagarov Bekzod Muzaffar o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK TIZIMIDA RAQOBAT MUHITINING SHAKLLANISH BOSQICHLARI VA TENDENSIYALARI.....	332
Qulmetov Mansurbek Ro'zmatovich	
USING ENGINEERING MODELS TO MEASURE SME RISKS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	340
Djumabayeva Dilobar Asatillayevna	
BANK FAOLIYATIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING ASOSIY MASALALARI.....	347
Yusufov Javohirtshoh Ozod o'g'li, Xolmirzayev Elbek Baxtiyorovich	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR JARAYONIDA TALABALARNING IJODKORLIK KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	353
Meyliyeva Shoxista Rustamovna	
ИНТЕГРАЛЬНАЯ ОЦЕНКА УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЦИФРОВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ТУРИЗМА И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТУРИСТСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ	358
Усманова Азиза Баходировна	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ELEKTR YORITISH MAHSULOTLARI BOZORINI INNOVATSION LOKALIZATSIYA ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH: DINAMIKA, TAHLIL VA PROGNOZ	363
Jurayev Murotjon Sotivoldiyevich	
HUUDUDLAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI BAHOLASH VA REYTINGLASH.....	371
Kosimov Bobir Abdigafarovich	
BALAND BINOLAR FASADLARINI PARDOZLASH TEXNOLOGIYALARINI EKSPLUATATSION ISHONCHLILIK VA XIZMAT MUDDATINI UZAYTIRISH ASOSIDA OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	376
Amirov Shavkat Rahmatullayevich	
ОСНОВЫ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ТРАНСПОРТНОЙ ЛОГИСТИКИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	383
Мурадов Алишер Курбанбаевич	
ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ БИЗНЕС-ПАРАДИГМЫ АГРОТУРИЗМА КАК УСЛОВИЕ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ ЦЕЛЕЙ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ	390
Усманова Диляфруз Каршиевна	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE REGIONAL STRUCTURE OF THE INDUSTRY OF NAVAI REGION	396
Uralov Eliboy Omonovich	
JISMONIY SHAXSLARNING MOL-MULK SOLIG'INI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA SAMARALI XORIJIY TAJRIBA	400
Safarova Shahzoda	
НАЛОГОВОЕ СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ И ПРАКТИКА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	405
Рафиева Зарина Хусановна	
INDUSTRY 4.0 SHAROITIDA SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INSON RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHNING ILMIY-AMALIY MASALALARI.....	410
Djuraeva Guzal Shavkatovna	

SUG'URTA TASHKILOTLARINING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	414
Xalikulova Shirin Utkir qizi	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA AKTIVLAR SIFATINI OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI.....	418
Ruziyev Baxtiyor Salimboyevich	
ВЗАИМОСВЯЗЬ УРОВНЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНОГО СЛОВАРЯ И ЛИДЕРСКИХ КАЧЕСТВ У ДЕТЕЙ МЛАДШЕГО ШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА.....	425
Рихсибоева Нигора Низомиддин кизи, Тоймухамедова Дилобар Хуснитдиновна	
TURIZM KORXONALARIDA INTEGRATSIYALASHGAN MARKETING KOMMUNIKATSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	434
Sobirjonov Asrorbek Sobitjon o'g'li	
KAM SUV TALABCHAN SEMENT OLISH UCHUN RATSIONAL TARKIBNI TADQIQ QILISH.....	440
X.V. Yusupov, Babayev Sultonbek Sunnat o'g'li	
ENHANCING THE EFFICIENCY OF ISLAMIC FINANCING MECHANISMS IN EMERGING ECONOMIES: EVIDENCE FROM MURABAHA-BASED INSTRUMENTS AND PUBLIC-PRIVATE INVESTMENT MODELS.....	445
Nazarov Nodirjon Namoz o'g'li	
TURIZM XIZMATLAR BOZORIDA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI OSHIRISH OMILLARI.....	453
Ibragimov Husen Ismailovich	
STUDIES ON OBTAINING AZOSUPERPHOSPHATE BY TREATING HIGH-CARBONATE, LOW-GRADE CENTRAL KYZYLKUM PHOSPHORITES WITH VARIOUS DOSAGES OF AMMONIUM SULFATE AND SULFURIC ACID.....	457
Saidov Hakimboy O'rinboyevich	
HUDUDIY SANOAT ISHLAB CHIQARISHNI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI.....	463
Avliyaqulov Xudoyberdi, Ollokulova Feruza Mansurovna	
NAVOIY VILOYATI SANOATI RIVOJLANISHINI BANDLIK VA INVESTITSIYA OQIMLARI ASOSIDA MODELLASHTIRISH.....	466
Baqoyev Husan Nuriddinovich	
TURIZM KORXONALARIDA INTEGRATSIYALASHGAN MARKETING KOMMUNIKATSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	474
Sobirjonov Asrorbek Sobitjon o'g'li	
YER VA SUV RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHNING IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARI VA INTEGRAL KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	480
Rustamov Umidjon Xayitboyevich	
AGROKLASTERLAR SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING EKONOMETRIK MODELLARI.....	485
O'rinboyev Ulug'bek Otabekovich	
TRANSPORT-LOGISTIKA TIZIMLARIDA XARAJATLARNI KAMAYTIRISH VA SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY YO'LLARI.....	494
Olimov Maqsudjon Komiljon o'g'li, Saydullayeva Dilnoza Komil qizi	
BENTONIT YORDAMIDA ISHLATILGAN TURBINA MOYLARINI TOZALASH ASOSIDA BAZAVIY MOY OLISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	502
Salomatov Behruz To'ymurodovich, Panoyev Nodir Shavkatovich, Safarov Jasur Alijon o'g'li	
INNOVATSION BOSHQARUV TIZIMLARIDA QAROR QABUL QILISH VA KOMMUNIKATSIYA SAMARADORLIGI.....	506
Sotvoldiyeva Xurliqo G'ayratjon qizi	

CHEMICAL-MINERALOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND DRY BENEFICIATION TECHNOLOGY OF
FELDSPAR FROM THE SULTAN UVAYS DEPOSIT 512
Buranova Dinara Baxtiyarovna

CHEMICAL–MINERALOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND DRY BENEFICIATION TECHNOLOGY OF FELDSPAR FROM THE SULTAN UVAYS DEPOSIT

Buranova Dinara Baxtiyarovna

Associate Professor of the Department of Chemical Technologies

PhD (Technical Sciences)

Urgench State University named after Abu Rayhan Beruni

E-mail: dinaraboranova@gmail.com

ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5403-268X

Abstract. This article presents a study of the chemical–mineralogical composition, granulometric distribution, and physicochemical properties of feldspar raw material obtained from the Sultan Uvays deposit located in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Lower Amu Darya region.

According to the results of X-ray diffraction analysis, the sample predominantly consists of microcline (60–65%), albite (21–25%), quartz (7–10%), and calcite (2–3%).

To obtain a concentrate suitable for the glass industry, a four-stage dry beneficiation technology has been developed and experimentally tested. This process includes magnetic separation ($H = 80\text{--}1300$ kA/m) and electrostatic separation methods.

The beneficiation results demonstrate that the SiO_2 content in the feldspar fraction increased from 68.44 wt.% to 74.60 wt.%, while the total iron content ($\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{FeO}$) decreased from 0.29 wt.% to 0.01 wt.%.

The obtained results confirm that feldspar from the Sultan Uvays deposit meets the requirements of GOST 22557-2019 and can be widely used as an independent raw material in the production of glass and enamel coatings.

Keywords: feldspar, magnetic separation, electrostatic separation, X-ray diffraction analysis, IR spectroscopy, BGMN/Profex Rietveld refinement, glass industry, Lower Amu Darya.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi, Quyi Amudaryo hududida joylashgan Sulton Uvays konidan olingan dala shpati xomashyosining kimyoviy-mineralogik tarkibi, granulometrik taqsimoti hamda fizik-kimyoviy xossalari tadqiq etilgan.

Rentgen difraksiya tahlil natijalariga ko‘ra, namuna asosan mikroklin (60–65%), albit (21–25%), kvarts (7–10%) va kalsitdan (2–3%) iboratligi aniqlangan.

Shisha sanoati uchun mos konsentrat olish maqsadida to‘rt bosqichli quruq boyitish texnologiyasi ishlab chiqilib, tajriba-sinovdan o‘tkazilgan. Ushbu jarayon magnit ajratish ($H = 80\text{--}1300$ kA/m) va elektrostatik ajratish usullarini o‘z ichiga oladi.

Boyitish natijalari dala shpati fraksiyasida SiO_2 miqdori 68,44 og‘.% dan 74,60 og‘.% gacha oshganini, umumiy temir miqdori ($\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{FeO}$) esa 0,29 og‘.% dan 0,01 og‘.% gacha kamayganini ko‘rsatdi.

Olingan natijalar Sulton Uvays koni dala shpati GOST 22557-2019 talablariga javob berishini hamda shisha va emal qoplamalari ishlab chiqarishda mustaqil xomashyo sifatida keng qo‘llanishi mumkinligini tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: dala shpati, magnit ajratish, elektrostatik ajratish, rentgen difraksiya tahlil, IQ spektroskopiya, BGMN/Profex Rietveld tahlili, shisha sanoati, Quyi Amudaryo.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены результаты исследования химико-минералогического состава, гранулометрического распределения и физико-химических свойств полевошпатового сырья, полученного с месторождения Султан Увайс, расположенного в Республике Каракалпакстан, регионе Нижней Амударьи.

Согласно результатам рентгенодифракционного анализа, образец преимущественно состоит из микроклина (60–65%), альбита (21–25%), кварца (7–10%) и кальцита (2–3%).

Для получения концентрата, пригодного для стекольной промышленности, разработана и экспериментально апробирована четырехстадийная технология сухого обогащения. Данный процесс включает методы магнитной сепарации ($H = 80\text{--}1300$ кА/м) и электростатической сепарации.

Результаты обогащения показали, что содержание SiO_2 в полевошпатовой фракции увеличилось с 68,44 мас.% до 74,60 мас.%, а общее содержание железа ($\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{FeO}$) снизилось с 0,29 мас.% до 0,01 мас.%.

Полученные результаты подтверждают, что полевой шпат месторождения Султан Увайс соответствует требованиям ГОСТ 22557-2019 и может широко использоваться в качестве самостоятельного сырья при производстве стекла и эмалевых покрытий.

Ключевые слова: полевой шпат, магнитная сепарация, электростатическая сепарация, рентгенодифракционный анализ, ИК-спектроскопия, уточнение структуры методом Ритвельда BGMN/Profex, стекольная промышленность, Нижняя Амударья.

INTRODUCTION

Feldspar minerals occupy a special place among alkaline aluminosilicate raw materials required for the glass industry. These minerals serve as a balanced source of silica, aluminum, and alkali elements, playing a crucial role in regulating the viscosity of the glass melt and reducing the sintering temperature. For this reason, global demand for feldspar raw materials has been steadily increasing [1-2].

The quality of feldspar raw materials is primarily determined by their chemical composition, mineralogical characteristics, and impurity content. In particular, iron-bearing minerals, titanium compounds, and excessive quartz negatively affect the optical and technological properties of glass products. Therefore, preliminary beneficiation and purification of feldspar ores are considered essential stages before their industrial application [3-4].

Various beneficiation methods, including flotation, magnetic separation, and electrostatic separation, are widely used in international practice to improve the quality of feldspar concentrates. Among them, dry beneficiation technologies are of particular interest due to their lower water consumption, environmental advantages, and economic efficiency, especially in arid regions where water resources are limited [5-6].

The Sultan Uvays deposit, located in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, represents a promising source of feldspar raw materials for the domestic glass and ceramic industries of Uzbekistan. However, the mineralogical composition and technological suitability of this deposit have not been sufficiently studied. Therefore, the present research aims to investigate the chemical–mineralogical properties of feldspar from the Sultan Uvays deposit and to develop an effective dry beneficiation technology for obtaining high-quality concentrate.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Uzbekistan, particularly the Lower Amu Darya basin, represents a highly promising region in this regard. The Sultan Uvays mountain massif, located within the territories of the Khorezm region and the Republic of Karakalpakstan, hosts significant deposits of potassium–sodium feldspar. However, these resources remain insufficiently studied and are still considered underexplored [3]. Although local industry partially utilizes this raw material, systematic scientific data on its mineralogical composition and beneficiation characteristics remain limited in the available literature.

The main challenge lies in the fact that feldspar rarely occurs in a sufficiently pure form suitable for direct industrial application. It must be purified from associated minerals, primarily free quartz and iron oxides. An increased content of iron oxides ($\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{FeO}$) leads to coloration defects in glass and enamel products and reduces their transparency [4]. Therefore, beneficiation has become an essential stage in the technological processing chain.

Two principal approaches are employed for raw material beneficiation: wet processing (flotation) and dry processing (magnetic and electrostatic separation). Although flotation ensures a high degree of purity, it is associated with significant water consumption, high reagent costs, and environmental challenges related to wastewater treatment [5]. In contrast, dry beneficiation technologies generate less waste, simplify the process, and significantly reduce production costs [6].

Previous international studies have shown that magnetic separation is particularly effective for removing iron-bearing minerals such as biotite, magnetite, and hematite, while electrostatic separation allows efficient differentiation between feldspar and quartz based on their surface electrical conductivity [7-8]. The combination of these methods makes it possible to obtain concentrates with improved chemical purity suitable for ceramic and glass applications.

Researchers have also emphasized that the efficiency of beneficiation strongly depends on particle size distribution, mineral liberation degree, and moisture content of the feed material. Proper grinding and classification prior to separation significantly improve concentrate recovery and reduce losses of valuable

feldspar fractions [9]. Therefore, optimization of pretreatment conditions is an important part of feldspar processing technology.

In Central Asia, limited scientific attention has been given to the technological assessment of feldspar deposits compared with other industrial minerals. This creates the need for detailed mineralogical and technological studies aimed at expanding the domestic raw material base and reducing dependence on imported feldspar concentrates for glass and ceramic production [10].

This study presents a comprehensive physicochemical characterization of feldspar from the Sultan Uvays deposit and demonstrates the efficiency of a dry beneficiation technology based on magnetic and electrostatic separation. The results contribute to evaluating the potential of this deposit as a reliable raw material source for the glass industry.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sampling and Sample Preparation. Samples for the study were collected from three different locations of the Sultan Uvays deposit (DSh-1, DSh-2, DSh-3). The initial samples consisted of lumps weighing 2–5 kg. Under laboratory conditions, primary crushing was performed using a jaw crusher, followed by further size reduction in cone and ball mills to obtain particle sizes in the range of 0.071–1.25 mm. Chemical analyses were carried out in accordance with the requirements of GOST 26423-86.

X-ray Diffraction Analysis (XRD). Quantitative mineralogical composition was determined using X-ray diffraction analysis. The diffraction patterns were processed using the BGMN/Profex software package based on the Rietveld refinement method. Unlike conventional qualitative approaches, this method enables precise quantitative determination of mineral phase proportions [7].

Infrared (IR) Spectroscopy. IR spectra of the samples were recorded in the range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} using a Fourier-transform spectrometer equipped with an ATR accessory. This method allows the identification of Si–O and Al–O bonding groups in silicates, as well as the presence of hydroxyl and carbonate groups. The obtained spectra were comparatively analyzed with the XRD results for validation [8].

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Elemental Analysis. The morphology and microstructure of the samples were studied using scanning electron microscopy. Quantitative elemental composition was determined by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). The analysis focused on the major elements: Si, Al, K, Na, Fe, and Ca.

Differential Thermogravimetric Analysis (DTG). Thermal properties of the samples were investigated using differential thermal and thermogravimetric analysis. The heating rate was set at 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, with the temperature increasing from 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The results revealed the relationship between temperature and endothermic as well as exothermic effects.

Thermal Treatment Experiments. Samples were subjected to thermal treatment in an electric furnace within the temperature range of 900–1300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 minutes. After each temperature stage, changes in crystalline phases were monitored using X-ray diffraction and IR spectroscopy.

Dry Beneficiation Technology. The beneficiation process was carried out in four sequential stages. The first three stages involved magnetic separation at different magnetic field intensities ($H = 80\text{--}100, 1000\text{--}1100,$ and 1300 kA/m) to remove magnetically susceptible minerals. In the fourth stage, electrostatic separation was applied to remove free quartz. This process utilizes the dielectric properties of quartz, characterized by a high electrical resistivity ($10^{16}\text{--}10^{21} \Omega\cdot\text{m}$).

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Chemical Composition. In industrial glass production based on feldspar from the Sultan Uvays deposit, particular attention is given to the granulometric composition of the raw material and its compliance with established state standards. This is because the particle size distribution of the batch components significantly influences their mixing behavior, as well as the efficiency of silicate and glass formation processes. For this purpose, three representative samples were selected from the deposit and subjected to chemical analysis (Table 1).

Table 1
Chemical composition of feldspar samples from the Sultan Uvays deposit (wt. %)¹

Samples	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O	TiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	LOI
DSh-1	68,66	16,53	0,30	0,57	0,31	10,00	2,93	0,04	0,14	0,52
DSh-2	68,16	17,15	0,27	0,53	0,31	9,98	2,88	0,05	0,16	0,51
DSh-3	68,45	16,75	0,31	0,56	0,29	9,96	2,95	0,06	0,16	0,51
Average	68,44	16,81	0,29	0,55	0,30	9,98	2,92	0,05	0,15	0,51

All three samples exhibited similar compositions, with no significant deviations observed. This indicates a relatively homogeneous mineralogical nature of the deposit.

The average SiO₂ content was 68.44 wt.%, which is typical for feldspar materials. The K₂O content of 9.98 wt.% suggests that the sample is potassium-rich and predominantly belongs to the microcline type of feldspar. The Fe₂O₃ content of 0.29 wt.% is slightly higher than the standard requirements, indicating the necessity for beneficiation. The Na₂O content of 2.92 wt.% confirms the presence of an albite fraction [9].

Mineralogical Composition (XRD Results). Processing of the X-ray diffraction patterns using the BGMN/Profex Rietveld refinement method revealed that the sample consists of the following mineral phases: microcline (60–65%), albite (21–25%), quartz (7–10%), and calcite (2–3%). In the initial diffraction pattern, the most intense diffraction peak ($d = 0.324$ nm) corresponds to the microcline mineral phase. Diffraction maxima associated with albite were observed at interplanar spacings of 0.646, 0.370, and 0.336 nm (Figure 1).

Figure 1. X-ray diffraction pattern of the feldspar sample from the Sultan Uvays deposit²

As can be seen from the mineralogical composition, the sample is predominantly composed of potassium–sodium feldspar with the general formula (K,Na)AlSi₃O₈. Although the calcite content is relatively low, its removal during the beneficiation stage is essential. From a thermal standpoint, calcite decomposes at approximately 791 °C with the release of CO₂, which may lead to the formation of gas-related defects during the firing process [10].

IR Spectroscopy Results. The IR spectrum of the sample exhibited characteristic absorption bands typical of natural aluminosilicate minerals (Figure 2).

The analysis revealed absorption bands at 443, 717, 726, 770, 996, and 1131 cm⁻¹, which correspond to Si–O vibrational modes characteristic of quartz. Vibrations observed in the regions of 416, 466, 535, 579, and 647 cm⁻¹ are typical for potassium–sodium feldspar and are associated with K–O and Na–O bonding groups (Figure 2).

1 author's development

2 author's development

Figure 2. IR spectrum of feldspar from the Sultan Uvays deposit³

The absorption band at 3415 cm^{-1} corresponds to the stretching vibrations of hydroxyl ($-\text{OH}$) groups, indicating the presence of structurally bound water. The IR spectroscopy results fully confirm the conclusions obtained from the X-ray diffraction analysis [11].

SEM and Elemental Analysis Results. To further validate the above findings, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) coupled with elemental analysis was performed. The quantitative distribution of the major elements in the sample was determined as follows (wt.%): Si – 31.98; Al – 8.89; K – 8.32; Na – 2.16, while other elements constitute the remaining fraction (Figure 3).

Figure 3. SEM image and corresponding spectrum of feldspar from the Sultan Uvays deposit⁴

These results are in good agreement with the chemical analysis data. The particle morphology is characterized by angular and irregular shapes, indicating that the particles were formed through mechanical crushing. SEM images also revealed the coexistence of different mineral phases within the same particles, which highlights the necessity of their separation through further mechanical processing and beneficiation.

Thermal Analysis Results. The DTG curve exhibited three endothermic and two exothermic effects. The endothermic effects observed at $96\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $281\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ correspond to the evaporation of hygroscopic and constitutionally bound water, respectively. The endothermic peak at $791\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ reflects the decomposition of calcite according to the reaction:

The exothermic effects were observed at $562\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, associated with the phase transformation of β -quartz to α -quartz, and at $843\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, corresponding to the partial decomposition of microcline and the formation of new crystalline phases [12].

X-ray diffraction analysis of the sample subjected to thermal treatment at $900\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ showed a decrease in the intensity of

³ author's development

⁴ author's development

diffraction peaks corresponding to albite and microcline, while the peaks associated with calcite disappeared completely. At 1300 °C, the sample was observed to have largely transformed into a glassy phase. The diffraction pattern exhibited a dominant peak ($d = 0.336 \text{ nm}$) corresponding to the anorthite mineral phase.

These results confirm the high-temperature mechanisms of glass phase formation [13] (Figure 4).

Figure 4. X-ray diffraction patterns of feldspar samples from the Sultan Uvays deposit after thermal treatment at 900 °C and 1300 °C⁵

Physico-Mechanical Properties of Minerals in Feldspar. The selection of an appropriate beneficiation method is largely determined by the differences in the physico-mechanical properties of the constituent minerals. These properties play a decisive role in the separation efficiency (Table 2).

**Table 2
Physico-mechanical properties of minerals in feldspar from the Sultan Uvays deposit⁶**

Mineral Name	Hardness (Mohs)	Density, g/cm ³	Compressive Strength, MPa	Water Absorption, wt. %
Quartz	7	2.65	250–400	0.1–0.2
Microcline	6	2.54–2.57	100–150	0.2–0.3
Albite	6	2.61–2.63	100–150	0.2–0.3
Calcite	3	2.71	100–150	0.8–0.9

As shown in Table 2, quartz (Mohs hardness = 7) is significantly harder than feldspar (Mohs hardness = 6). Calcite, on the other hand, is the softest mineral (Mohs hardness = 3) and exhibits the highest water absorption capacity (0.8–0.9%).

These differences result in non-uniform fragmentation of minerals during the crushing process, which facilitates selective separation during beneficiation [14].

Results of Dry Beneficiation. The beneficiation process was carried out for particles in the size range of 0.071–1.25 mm. As a result of the four-stage process, the minerals were separated as follows:

First stage ($H = 80\text{--}100 \text{ kA/m}$): strongly magnetic minerals, such as magnetite, were removed.

Second stage ($H = 1000\text{--}1100 \text{ kA/m}$): weakly magnetic minerals, including hematite, biotite, and muscovite, were separated.

Third stage ($H = 1300 \text{ kA/m}$): minerals such as muscovite, tourmaline, epidote, and iron-bearing feldspars were primarily removed at this stage.

Fourth stage (electrostatic separation): free quartz was separated from the non-magnetic fraction based on its dielectric properties (Table 3).

**Table 3
Chemical composition of separated and beneficiated samples after processing (wt.%)⁷**

Mineral Phase	Yield, wt. %	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O	Fe ₂ O ₃ + FeO
Mica	2.82	48.65	20.10	11.35	4.65	0.10
Quartz	18.40	94.60	2.03	1.56	1.39	0.02
Feldspar	70.23	74.60	13.64	9.01	1.08	0.01
Tailings	8.55	38.40	20.45	12.23	3.96	4.56

5 author’s development

6 author’s development

7 author’s development

As shown in Table 3, the feldspar fraction accounts for 70.23% of the total mass. As a result of beneficiation, the SiO_2 content increased from 68.44 wt.% to 74.60 wt.%, while Al_2O_3 decreased from 16.81 wt.% to 13.64 wt.%.

Most importantly, the total iron content ($\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{FeO}$) decreased from 0.29 wt.% to 0.01 wt.%, representing a 29-fold reduction. This result fully meets the color and transparency requirements of the glass industry. The waste fraction constituted only 8.55 wt.%, which is significantly lower than that typically observed in flotation-based beneficiation processes [15].

Description of the Technological Scheme. Based on the obtained experimental results, the following sequential technological scheme is proposed for the dry beneficiation of feldspar from the Sultan Uvays deposit (Figure 5).

Initially, raw material with a particle size of +300 mm is fed through a receiving hopper into a jaw crusher and screened using a grizzly screen. The +25 mm fraction is returned for re-crushing.

The fine fraction is dried in a rotary drum dryer to a moisture content of 0.5%. The dried material is then ground in a cone inertial crusher to a particle size of -1.25 mm. In the next stage, a magnetic separator removes iron-bearing minerals. The beneficiated product is further ground in a vibration mill and classified in an air separator. At this stage, free quartz is separated from the fine fraction using an electrostatic separator based on its dielectric properties. The final feldspar concentrate is collected in a pulse collector and transferred to the product storage bunker [16] (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Processing flowsheet of Sultan Uvays feldspar ore⁸

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the comprehensive investigations conducted, the following conclusions can be drawn. Feldspar from the Sultan Uvays deposit consists mainly of microcline (60–65%), albite (21–25%), quartz (7–10%), and calcite (2–3%), with an average chemical composition of SiO_2 – 68.44 wt.%, Al_2O_3 – 16.81 wt.%, K_2O – 9.98 wt.%, Na_2O – 2.92 wt.%, and Fe_2O_3 – 0.29 wt.%. These values fall within the acceptable limits defined by GOST 22557-2019.

The results of IR spectroscopy, SEM–EDX, and DTG analyses independently confirmed the findings of X-ray diffraction analysis. Thermal studies showed that the sample undergoes complete transformation into a glassy phase at 1300 °C, indicating its suitability as a raw material for glass and enamel production.

The four-stage dry beneficiation technology based on magnetic separation (three stages, $H = 80$ –1300 kA/m) and electrostatic separation reduced the $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{FeO}$ content from 0.29 wt.% to 0.01 wt.%, while increasing the SiO_2 content to 74.60 wt.%. The waste fraction was limited to 8.55 wt.%, demonstrating a significant advantage over flotation methods.

The proposed dry beneficiation technology does not require water or chemical reagents, features a simple process flow, and is easy to control. These advantages make it both environmentally and economically favorable, particularly under Central Asian conditions where water conservation is critically important. Future work will focus on pilot-scale testing of the proposed technology, followed by the design of a full-scale industrial processing line. Additionally, it is planned to evaluate the potential use of the separated quartz fraction (SiO_2 – 94.60 wt.%) as an alternative to conventional quartz sand.

REFERENCES

1. Hafner, S. The crystal chemistry of the common rock-forming silicates. // *Mineralogical Magazine*. – 2019. – Vol. 83, No. 4. – P. 571–589.
2. Andreev, A.V., Kostychev, I.A. Ispolzovaniye polevykh shpatov v steklokeramicheskoy promyshlennosti. // *Steklo i keramika*. – 2021. – No. 3. – P. 14–20.
3. Yusupov, O'., Xolmatov, B. *O'zbekiston mineral resurslarining sanoatdagi o'rni*. – Toshkent: Fan, 2020. – 312 p.
4. Bolen, W.P. *Feldspar and nepheline syenite: USGS Minerals Yearbook*. – Washington: USGS, 2022. – P. 26.1–26.5.
5. Wills, B.A., Finch, J.A. *Wills' Mineral Processing Technology*. 8th ed. – Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann, 2016. – 512 p.
6. Ferreira, O.P., Alves, O.L. Dry magnetic separation of feldspar from quartz: effects of particle size and field intensity. // *Minerals Engineering*. – 2018. – Vol. 121. – P. 155–162.
7. Döbelin, N., Kleeberg, R. Profex: a graphical user interface for the Rietveld refinement program BGMN. // *Journal of Applied Crystallography*. – 2015. – Vol. 48. – P. 1573–1580.
8. Buranova, D.B. Main characteristics of quartz-feldspar sands from the Khiva deposit, and the physico-chemical and technological fundamentals of obtaining an enriched concentrate. // *Kompleksnoe Ispolzovanie Mineralnogo Syra*. – 2027. – Vol. 340, No. 1. – P. 37–44.
9. GOST 22557-2019. *Polevye shpaty dlya stekol'noy promyshlennosti*. – Moskva: Standartinform, 2019. – 18 p.
10. Redfern, S.A.T. The thermodynamics of calcite decomposition. // *Contributions to Mineralogy and Petrology*. – 2016. – Vol. 171. – P. 1–12.
11. Sitarz, M., Mozgawa, W., Handke, M. Vibrational spectra of complex ring silicate anions: method of recognition. // *Journal of Molecular Structure*. – 2017. – Vol. 1135. – P. 184–190.
12. Zhang, G., Gao, J. Thermal phase transformations in potassium feldspar studied by differential thermal analysis. // *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*. – 2020. – Vol. 40, No. 3. – P. 772–778.
13. Babayev, Z.K., Masharipova, S.M., Buranova, D.B., & Ataeva, F.A. Improving the stability of restoration inorganic wall materials in the monuments of ancient Khiva. // *Austrian Journal of Technical and Natural Sciences*. – 2021. – No. 1–2. – P. 49–53.
14. Buranova, D.B., Yunusov, M.Y., Babaev, Z.K., Kurambaev, Sh.R., & Atashev, E.A. The physico-chemical analysis of quartz sand of Khiva deposit. // *RA Journal of Applied Research*. – 2023. – Vol. 9, No. 10. – P. 506–509.
15. Dunham, S., Komar, D. Flotation reagent consumption and waste production in silicate mineral processing. // *Minerals*. – 2020. – Vol. 10, No. 7. – P. 621.
16. Karimov, N.X., Toshmatov, E.N. Quruq boyitish texnologiyalari va ularning sanoatda qo'llanilishi. // *O'zbek kimyo jurnali*. – 2022. – No. 2. – P. 44–52.

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Abdurahmon Qurbonov

2026. № 4

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

t.me/yait_2100